

Acknowledgement

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Quantitative Studies on the Water Decomposition Product of Ethereal Blue perchromate Prepared with 5-Sulphosalicylic acid : A Colorimetric Determination*

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THOUGH several workers¹⁻⁷ have tried to establish the presence of Cr(III) along with Cr(VI) in various decomposition products of ethereal blue perchromate, no work is on record for colorimetric determination of chromium present in the water decomposition product using *s*-diphenylcarbazide as a sensitive complexing agent.⁸

Hence to ascertain the composition of the water decomposition product, $(\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}\text{Su})_3[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}(\text{Cr}_2^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_7)_3]$, of ethereal blue perchromate prepared in presence of 5-sulphosalicylic acid, reported earlier⁶⁻⁷, estimation of chromium has been carried out colorimetrically.

Experimental

Ethereal blue perchromate was prepared in the presence of 5-sulphosalicylic acid and then it was decomposed in 25 ml of double distilled water in the usual way^{3,6}. As per recommended procedure⁸ an aliquot of the water decomposition product (dichromate) was treated with *s*-diphenylcarbazide solution

and within 5 mins a violet coloured Cr(VI) complex was obtained. Next, the other aliquot of the test solution was oxidised to convert Cr(III) into Cr(VI) and then subjected to diphenylcarbazide treatment.

Transmittance (*T*) measurements of test and standard (dichromate) solutions after diphenylcarbazide treatment were recorded on "Aimil" photo colorimeter using 1 cm glass cell and a green filter having the transmission maximum at about 540 nm. Solvent blank containing approximate concentration of Cr(III) and sulphosalicylate ion was set up at 100% transmittance. Alternatively, to avoid the interference of these concentrations violet complex was extracted with carbontetrachloride. A standard calibration curve was obtained by plotting optical densities, $D = \log 1/T$, against varying volumes (conc. 50 μ gm/ml) of the standard solution which shows validity of Lambert-Beer's law.

Discussion

From the calibration curve the concentration of test solutions (unoxidised and oxidised) was ascertained. The increased concentration of oxidised test solution shows the presence of Cr(III) along with Cr(VI) in the decomposition product. The ratio between the concentration of Cr(VI) and oxidisable Cr(III) is 4.65 : 1.50 which comes nearly to the value 3 : 1 reported earlier⁶⁻⁷.

Thus ratio and inferences are in quite agreement with the formula $(\text{CrSu})_3[\text{Cr}(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3]$ for water decomposition product corresponding to the parent
 $\begin{matrix} \text{III} & \text{III} & \text{VI} \\ \text{III} & \text{III} & \text{VI} \end{matrix}$
 blue perchromate, $(\text{CrSu})_3[\text{Cr}(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3]$, where Su is bivalent sulphosalicylate ion.

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